

Table S3. Univariate mixed-effects logistic regression for low birth weight in *P. falciparum* positive women at delivery

Odds ratios (OR) with 95% CI and *p* values are presented of univariate models (*p* values <0.05 in bold).

<i>dhfr</i> Fixed effect(s)	LBW			
	OR	[95%CI]		<i>p</i>
Triple <i>dhfr</i> mutation	0.95	0.39	2.30	0.905
Age (10 years)	0.53	0.28	0.99	0.046
Gravidity	0.74	0.60	0.91	0.004
Season#	1.54	0.49	4.89	0.463
IPTp-SP doses	0.47	0.28	0.78	0.003
AL	1.09	0.69	1.75	0.705

AL = artemether-lumefantrine therapy; LBW = low birth weight; # low transmission season = 0, high transmission season = 1;